

NUMERICAL SOLUTION OF VARIOUS ONE AND TWO STEPS METHODS USING GAUSS LOBATTO METHOD FOR APPROXIMATING TO SOLVE FREDHOLM EQUATION

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Abstract

In this paper, we present a new analytical technique to obtaining the analytical approximate solutions for system of Fredholm integral equations based on the use of the Gauss Lobatto Method for approximating. We used a compute of approximate roots of Legendre polynomial by recursive relation. In the iterative method, we chose a good initial guess and initial approximation. We create the new efficient method for solving Fredholm integral and integro-differential equations of the second kind and the systems which consist such equations.

Keywords: Numerical Method, Fredholm Equation, Gauss Lobatto Method.

1. INTRODUCTION

In mathematics, the Fredholm integral equation is an integral equation whose solution gives rise to Fredholm theory, the theory has been developed by Fredholm in 1900, then flourished by the hands of Hilbert, Frechet, Riesz, Lebesgue, and other famous mathematicians. The systems of Fredholm integral equations occur frequently in applied mathematics, theoretical physics, engineering, biology, mathematical modeling.

An integral equation is an equation containing an unknown function under an integral operator. The Adomian decomposition method has been receiving much attention in recent years in applied mathematics in general, and in the area of series solutions in particular [5, 7, 8, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22]. The method was proved to be powerful, effective, and can easily handle a wide class of linear or nonlinear, ordinary or partial differential equations, and linear and non-linear integral equations. The ADM demonstrates fast convergence of the solution and therefore provides several significant advantages.

The method will be successfully used to handle most types of ordinary differential equations that appear in several physical models and scientific applications. Integral equations appear in many types. The types depend mainly on the limits of integration and the kernel of the equation. Sometimes we cannot obtain exact solutions. In this case we determine the solution in a series form that may converge to exact solution if such a solution exists. Other series may not give exact solution, and in this case the obtained series can be used for numerical purposes.

The more terms that we determine the higher accuracy level that we can achieve. Currently, the method of choice for computing the $(n + 2)$ point GL quadrature rule for any measure of integration is to first generate the Jacobi matrix of order $(n + 2)$ for the measure at hand, then modify the three elements at the right lower corner of the matrix in a manner proposed in 1973 by Golub, and finally compute the eigenvalues and first components of the respective eigenvectors to produce the nodes and weights of the quadrature rule.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the Fredholm Equation and Legendre Gauss Lobatto quadrature root. Section 3 presented Matrix with unknown vectors [21, 22]. Section 4 deals the solution by Integral. Section 5 we presented the numerical description of Legendre polynomial solution of the second ordinary differential equation. Finally, we conclude.

2. FREDHOLM EQUATION AND LEGENDRE GAUSS LOBATTO QUADRATURE ROOT

$$\int_{\Omega} f(x, y)v(x, y)dxdy = \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^N f(x_i, y_j)v(x_i, y_j)w_iw_j, \text{ where } w_i, w_j \text{ are weights.}$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \Delta u \cdot \Delta v \, dxdy = \int_{\Omega} (\partial_x u \cdot \partial_x v + \partial_y u \cdot \partial_y v) \, dxdy, \text{ where } \partial_x u = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}(x, y)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \Delta u \cdot \Delta v \, dxdy = \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^N (\partial_x u \partial_x v + \partial_y u \partial_y v)(x_i, y_j)w_iw_j.$$

The test function $v(x, y) = h_i(x)h_j(y)$, using $v(x, y) = h_i(x)h_j(y)$

$$\int_{\Omega} f(x, y)v(x, y) \, dx \, dy = \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^N f(x_i, y_j)v(x_i, y_j)w_iw_j$$

$$\int_{\Omega} f(x, y)h_i(x)h_j(y) \, dx \, dy = f(x_i, y_j)w_iw_j.$$

Let $K=(2\text{-elements})$ or $K=(4\text{-elements})$

$$Y_N = \left\{ w \in L^2(\Omega); w|_{\Omega_k} \in \mathbb{P}_N(\Omega_k), k = 1, \dots, K \right\}.$$

Space of piecewise polynomial function for Dirichlet problem, we see K solution in $X_N = Y_N \cap H_0^1(\Omega)$

$$X_N = \left\{ w \in Y_N, w = 0 \text{ on } \partial\Omega, \forall k, l, w^k|_{\Gamma_{kl}} = w^l|_{\Gamma_{kl}} \right\}$$

where $\Gamma_{kl} = \partial\Omega_k \cap \partial\Omega_l$ interface between subdermain

$$\int_{\Omega} U(x, y) \, dxdy = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^N \varphi(x_i^k, y_j^k) \underbrace{\alpha_k \beta_k}_{\text{Jacobian}} w_i w_j$$

and

$$\int_{\Omega} f(x, y)v(x, y) \, dxdy = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^N f(x_i^k, y_j^k) v(x_i^k, y_j^k) \underbrace{\alpha_k \beta_k}_{\text{Jacobian}} w_i w_j.$$

Let $f^k = f|_{\Omega_k} \circ \Lambda_k$; $u^k = u|_{\Omega_k} \circ \Lambda_k$; $v^k = v|_{\Omega_k} \circ \Lambda_k$

$$\int_{\Omega} f(x, y) \sigma(x, y) dx dy = \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^N f^k(\xi_i, \xi_j) v(\xi_i, \xi_j) \alpha_k \beta_k w_i w_j \text{ where } (\xi_i, \xi_j) \in [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$$

because:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \varphi(x, y) dx dy &= \sum_{k=1}^K \int_{\Omega_k} \varphi(x, y) dx dy \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^K \int_{[-1,1] \times [-1,1]} \varphi^k(\xi, \eta) |J_k(\xi, \eta)| d\xi d\eta \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} J_k(\xi, \eta) &= \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} \frac{\partial y}{\partial \eta} - \frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta} \frac{\partial y}{\partial \xi} \\ &= \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta} \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \eta} \end{vmatrix} = \alpha_k \beta_k \\ \int_{\Omega} \varphi(x, y) v(x, y) dx dy &= \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^N \tilde{f}^k(\xi_i, \xi_j) v^k(\xi_i, \xi_j) |J_k(\xi_i, \xi_j)| \\ \int_{\Omega} f(x, y) v(x, y) dx dy &= \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^N \tilde{f}^k(\xi_i, \xi_j) v^k(\xi_i, \xi_j) |J_k| w_i w_j \end{aligned}$$

where $|J_k| = |J_k^k(\xi_i, \xi_j)|$.

Let $v^k(x, y) = h_l^k(x) h_s^k(y)$ then

$$\sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^N \tilde{f}^k(\xi_i, \xi_j) v^k(\xi_i, \xi_j) |J^k| w_i w_j = \sum_{i=0}^N \sum_{j=0}^N \tilde{f}^k(\xi_i, \xi_j) h_l^k(\xi_i) h_s^k(\xi_j) |J^k| w_i w_j$$

$$h_l^k = \delta_{il} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = l \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} = \tilde{f}^k(\xi_l, \xi_s) |Y^k(\xi_l, \xi_s)| w_l w_s.$$

Now we have

$$\int_{\Omega} f(x, y) v(x, y) dx dy = \sum_{k=1}^K \tilde{f}^k(\xi_l, \xi_s) |J^k(\xi_l, \xi_s)| w_l w_s.$$

Here $\tilde{f}^k = f^k \circ \Lambda_k$, where Λ_k is the mapping from Ω to Ω_k

$$\sum_{k=0}^K \int_{\Omega_k} \nabla u^k(x, y) \Delta v^k(x, y) dx dy =$$

we have

$$\int_{\Omega_k} \nabla u^k(x, y) \nabla v^k(x, y) dx dy = \int_{\Omega} \nabla \tilde{u}^k(\xi, \eta) \nabla \tilde{v}^k(\xi, \eta) |J^k(\xi, \eta)| d\xi d\eta$$

where $\tilde{u}^k(\xi, \eta) = u^k \circ \wedge_k(\xi, \eta)$

$$u^k(x, y) = u^k(\wedge_k(\xi, \eta)) = \tilde{u}^k(\xi, \eta)$$

$$v^k(x, y) = v^k(\wedge_k(\xi, \eta)) = \tilde{v}^k(\xi, \eta)$$

$$J^k(\xi, \eta) = \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial x}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial x}{\partial \eta} \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial y}{\partial \eta} \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\tilde{u}^k(\xi, \eta) = \sum_{i,j=0}^N \tilde{U}_{i,j}^k h_i^k(\xi) h_j^k(\eta)$$

$$\tilde{v}^k(\xi, \eta) = h_l^k(\xi) h_s^k(\eta)$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \Delta \tilde{u}^k(\xi, \eta) \Delta \tilde{v}^k(\xi, \eta) |J^k(\xi, \eta)| d\xi d\eta \\ &= \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \tilde{U}_{ij}^k(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \tilde{v}^k(\xi, \eta) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \tilde{u}^k(\xi, \eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \tilde{v}^k(\xi, \eta) \right) |J^k(\xi, \eta)| d\xi d\eta \\ &= \sum_{i,j=0}^N \tilde{u}_{ij}^k \int_{\Omega} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (h_i^k(\xi) h_j^k(\xi)) \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (h_l^k(\xi) h_s^k(\eta)) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} (h_i^k(\xi) h_j^k(\xi)) \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} (h_l^k(\xi) h_s^k(\eta)) \right\} |J^k(\xi, \eta)| d\xi d\eta \\ &= \sum_{i,j=0}^N \tilde{U}_{ij}^k \int_{\Omega} \left(h_i^{k'}(\xi) h_j^k(\xi) h_l^{k'}(\xi) h_s^k(\eta) + h_i^k(\xi) h_j^{k'}(\xi) h_l^k(\xi) h_s^k(\eta) \right) |J^k(\xi, \eta)| d\xi d\eta. \end{aligned}$$

First

$$\int_{\Omega} h_l^{k'}(\xi) h_j^k(\xi) h_l^{k'}(\xi) h_s^k(\eta) |J^k(\xi, \eta)| d\eta d\xi = \sum_{r,m} h_l^{k'}(\xi_r) h_j^k(\eta_m) h_l^{k'}(\xi_r) h_s^k(\eta_m) |J^k(\xi_r, \eta_m)| w_r w_m.$$

Using $h_j^k(\eta_m) = \delta_{jm}$, $h_s^k(\eta_m) = \delta_{ms}$

3. MATRIX WITH UNKNOWN VECTORS

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{m=0}^N w_m w_l \left\{ \sum_{\substack{l=0, \\ 1 \neq k}}^{N-1} u_{il} D_{ml} D_{mk} + u_{kl} D_{mk} D_{ml} \right\} \\ &+ \sum_{n=0}^N w_k w_n \left\{ \sum_{\substack{j=1, \\ d \neq l}}^{N-1} v_{kj} D_{nj} D_{nl} + u_{kl} D_{nl} D_{nl} \right\} \\ &= w_k w_l f(x_k, y_l), \quad \forall k, l = 1, \dots, N-1 \end{aligned}$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{\substack{l=0, \\ 1 \neq k}}^{N-1} w_l u_{1l} \left\{ \sum_{m=0}^N W_m D_{mi} D_{mk} \right\} + \left(w_l \sum_{m=0}^N W_m D_{mk}^2 \right) u_{kl} \\
 & + w_k u_{kj} \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^N w_n D_{nj} D_{nl} \right\} + \left(w_k \sum_{n=0}^N w_n D_{nl}^2 \right) u_{kl} \\
 & = w_k w_l f(x_k, y_l) \\
 \Rightarrow & w_l \sum_{\substack{i=1, \\ l \neq k}}^{N-1} u_{1l} \left(\sum_{m=0}^N w_m D_{mi} D_{mk} \right) + w_k \sum_{\substack{d=1, \\ d \neq 1}}^{N-1} u_{kj} \left(\sum_{n=0}^N w_n D_{nj} D_{nl} \right) + \\
 & \left\{ w_l \sum_{m=0}^N w_m D_{mk}^2 + w_k \sum_{n=0}^N w_n D_{nl}^2 \right\} u_{kl} \\
 & = w_k w_l f(x_k, x_l)
 \end{aligned}$$

For simplicity, we consider $N = 4$ but at the boundary the solution is known and we have $u = 0$. The unknown vectors is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_{11} \\ u_{12} \\ u_{13} \\ u_{21} \\ u_{22} \\ u_{23} \\ u_{31} \\ u_{32} \\ u_{33} \end{bmatrix}$$

our unknown vector is

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \\ U_6 \\ U_7 \\ U_8 \\ U_9 \end{bmatrix}$$

the unknown vector is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_{11} \\ u_{12} \\ u_{13} \\ u_{21} \\ u_{22} \\ u_{23} \\ u_{31} \\ u_{32} \\ u_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \\ U_6 \\ U_7 \\ U_8 \\ U_9 \end{bmatrix}$$

we denote by $F_{lk} = w_k w_l f(x_k, y_l)$.

Let us $f(x), k = 1$ and $l = 1$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} & w_1 \sum_{i=1}^3 E_{1i} u_{i1} + w_1 \sum_{\substack{d=1, \\ d \neq 1}}^3 u_{ij} E_{1j} + \{u_1 E_{11} + u_1 E_{11}\} u_{11} = F_{11} \\ & w_1 (E_{12} u_{21} + E_{13} u_{31}) + w_1 (u_{12} E_{12} + u_{13} E_{13}) + \{w_1 E_{11} + u_1 E_{11}\} u_{11} = F_{11} \\ & w_1 E_{12} \sqcup_{21} + w_1 E_{13} \sqcup_{31} + w_1 E_{12} \sqcup_{12} + w_1 E_{13} \sqcup_{13} + 2w_1 E_{11} \sqcup_{11} = F_{11} \\ & \sum_{\substack{l=0, \\ l \neq k}}^{N-1} w_l u_{1l} \left\{ \sum_{m=0}^N w_m D_{mi} D_{mk} \right\} + \left(w_l \sum_{m=0}^N w_m D_{mk}^2 \right) u_{kl} \\ & + \sum_{\substack{d=1, \\ d \neq l}}^{N-1} w_k u_{kj} \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^N w_n D_{nj} D_{nl} \right\} + \left(w_k \sum_{n=0}^N w_n D_{nl}^2 \right) U_{kl} = W_k w_l f(x_k, y_l) \\ \Rightarrow & W_l \sum_{\substack{l=1, \\ l \neq k}}^{N-1} u_{1l} \left(\sum_{m=0}^N w_m D_{mi} D_{mk} \right) + w_k \sum_{\substack{d=1, \\ d \neq l}}^{N-1} u_{kj} \left(\sum_{n=0}^N w_n D_{nj} D_{nl} \right) \\ & + \left\{ w_l \sum_{m=0}^N w_m D_{mk}^2 + w_k \sum_{n=0}^N w_n D_{nl}^2 \right\} u_{kl} =_k w_l f(x_k, y_l) \end{aligned}$$

these nodes will be numbered as:

$$u_{11} = U_1, u_{21} = U_4, u_{31} = U_7, u_{12} = U_2, u_{22} = U_5, u_{32} = U_8$$

$u_{13} = U_3, u_{23} = U_6, u_{33} = U_9$ we will write matrix with unknown vectors is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} U_1 \\ U_2 \\ U_3 \\ U_4 \\ U_5 \\ U_6 \\ U_7 \\ U_8 \\ U_9 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\begin{aligned} k = 1, l = 1 \\ k = 1, l = 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$k = 1, l = 3 \begin{pmatrix} 2w_1E_{11} & w_1E_{12} & w_1E_{13} & w_1E_{12} & 0 & 0 & w_1E_{13} & 0 & 0 \\ w_1E_{21} & \gamma_{12} & w_1E_{23} & 0 & w_2E_{12} & 0 & 0 & w_2E_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} U_{11} \\ U_{12} \\ U_{13} \\ U_{14} \\ U_{15} \\ U_{16} \\ U_{17} \\ U_{18} \\ U_{19} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} F_{11} \\ F_{12} \\ F_{13} \\ F_{14} \\ F_{15} \\ F_{16} \\ F_{17} \\ F_{18} \\ F_{19} \end{pmatrix}$$

second equation $k = 1, l = 2$

$$\begin{aligned} u_2(U_{22}E_{12} + u_{32}E_{13}) + w_1(U_{11}E_{21} + u_{13}E_{23}) + \underbrace{\{w_2E_{11} + w_1E_{22}\}}_{\gamma_{12}} u_{12} = F_{21} \\ w_2E_{12}U_{22} + w_2E_{13}U_{32} + w_1E_{21}U_{11} + w_1E_{23}U_{13} + \gamma_{12}u_{12} = F_{21}. \end{aligned}$$

4. SOLUTION BY INTEGRAL

Let

$$\begin{cases} -u''(x) + u(x) = f(x) \\ u(-1) = 0 \\ u(1) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

We define the set

$$V^N = \{v \in P_N([-1, 1]) : v(-1) = v(1) = 0\}$$

where $P_N([-1, 1])$ is the space of polynomials of degree at most N over the range $[-1, 1]$, we multiply the strong form by a test function and we integrate over the range $[-1, 1]$ we chose $v \in V^N$ as test function then [21, 22]

$$\int_{-1}^1 -u''(x)v(x)dx + \int_{-1}^1 u(x)v(x)dx = \int_{-1}^1 f(x)v(x)dx.$$

Integrating by parts

$$[-u'(x)v(x)]_{-1}^1 - \int_{-1}^1 (-u'(x))v'(x)dx + \int_{-1}^1 u(x)v(x)dx = \int_{-1}^1 f(x)v(x)dx \quad (2)$$

the first term in (2) equal 0 because $v(-1) = v(1) = 0$ then (2) becomes

$$\int_{-1}^1 (u'(x))v'(x)dx + \int_{-1}^1 u(x)v(x)dx = \int_{-1}^1 f(x)v(x)dx. \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) called weak formulation. The approximate solution is expanded using Lagrange interpolation based on the Gauss Lobatto Legendre points; i.e

$$u_N(x) = \sum_{i=0}^N c_i h_i(x)$$

Where

$$h_i(x) = \frac{(1-x^2)L'_N(x)}{N(N+1)L_N(x_i)(x-x_i)}$$

and $x_i = 0, \dots, N$ and Gauss Lobatto Legendre points with $x_0 = -1$, $x_N = 1$ and c_i are the unknowns coefficients with

$$u(x_i) \simeq u_N(x_i) = c_i, \quad h_i(x_N) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } i = N \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

We recall that the Legendre Gauss Lobatto quadrature root must be computed numerically where

$$(1-x^2)L'_N(x) = 0$$

$$w_i = \frac{2}{N(N+1)L_N^2(x_i)}, \quad i = 0, \dots, N$$

Quadrature rule:

$$\int_{-1}^1 \phi(x) dx = \sum_{i=0}^N w_i \phi(x_i) \quad (4)$$

the approximate solution is:

$$u_N(-1) = \sum_{i=0}^N c_i h_i(x). \quad (5)$$

Boundary condition: $x = x_0 = -1$, $u_N(-1) = 0$; $-1 = x_0$.

$$0 = u_N(x_0) = \sum_{i=0}^N c_i h_i(x_0) = c_0 h_0(x_0) + \sum_{i=1}^N c_i h_i(x_0), \quad c_0 = 0.$$

Boundary condition at $x = x_N = 1$ gives

$$0 = u_N(1) = \sum_{i=0}^N c_i h_i(x_N) = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} c_i h_i(x_N) + c_N h_N(x_N), \quad c_N = 0.$$

Then

$$u_N(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} c_i h_i(x).$$

Plugging u_N into the weak form see (3) and we chose $v(x) = h_j(x)$, we have:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N-1} c_i \int_{-1}^1 h_i'(x) h_j'(x) dx + \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} c_i \int_{-1}^1 h_i(x) h_j(x) dx = \int_{-1}^1 f(x) h_j(x) dx, \quad j = 1, \dots, N-1$$

using quadrature rule to compute both integral:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{-1}^1 h_i'(x) h_j'(x) dx &\simeq \sum_{k=0}^N w_k h_i'(x_k) h_j'(x_k) \\ \int_{-1}^1 f(x) h_j(x) dx &\simeq \sum_{k=0}^N w_k f(x_k) h_j(x_k) \\ \int_{-1}^1 h_i(x) h_j(x) dx &\simeq \sum_{k=0}^N w_k h_i(x_k) h_j(x_k) \end{aligned}$$

then we have

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} c_i \left(\sum_{k=0}^N w_k h_i'(x_k) h_j'(x_k) \right) + \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} c_i \left(\sum_{k=0}^N w_k h_i(x_k) h_j(x_k) \right) = \sum_{k=0}^N w_k f(x_k) h_j(x_k), \quad j = 1, \dots, N-1.$$

Let

$$\begin{aligned} a_{ji} &= \sum_{k=0}^N w_k h_i'(x_k) h_j'(x_k) \\ f_j &= \sum_{k=0}^N w_k f(x_k) h_j(x_k) \end{aligned}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} f_j &= w_j f(x_j) \\ \left(\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} c_i a_{ji} + c_j w_j \right) &= f_j, \quad j, i = 1, \dots, N-1 \end{aligned}$$

we have $N - 1$ equations and $N - 1$ unknowns. We obtain the matrix problem $AU = F$ where

$$A = (a_{ji})_{j,i=1,\dots,N-1} + \text{diag}(w_1, \dots, w_{N-1})$$

And

$$F = (f_j)_{j=1,\dots,N-1}^T$$

where T indicate the transpose of vector

$$a_{ji} = \sum_{k=0}^N w_k h'_i(x_k) h'_j(x_k)$$

if we denote by $D_{kj} = h'_j(x_i)$ then we, have

and we, have

$$D_{kj} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{(x_k - x_j)} \frac{L_N(x_k)}{L_N(x_j)} & j \neq k \\ 0, & 1 \leq j = k \leq N - 1 \\ -\frac{N(N+1)}{4} & j = k = 0 \\ \frac{N(N+1)}{4} & j = k = N \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

equation (6) is the differentiation matrix.

5. NUMERICAL DESCRIPTION

We recall the different definition of error not will be used in our study. The absolute error is defined as:

$$\text{error}_{Ab} = |u_N - u_{\text{exact}}|$$

the relative error is given by:

$$\text{error}_R = \frac{|u_N - u_{\text{exact}}|}{|u_{\text{exact}}|}$$

the L^2 norm of error is

$$\| \text{error}_{Ab} \|_{L^2} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^N w_i (\text{error}_{Ab})^2}$$

the L^2 relative norm of error is

$$\| \text{error}_R \|_{L^2} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^N w_i (\text{error}_{Ab})^2}}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^N w_i (u_{exact})^2}}$$

$$\text{Error}(x) = |u^N - u_{exact}| \quad \text{function}$$

we present a simple strategy that allow us to compute the $(x_i)_{i=0, \dots, N}$ roots of $h_i(x)$. the method used is described as follows: To find $(x_i)_{i=0, \dots, N}$ the roots of $h_i(x)$ or the roots of $(1-x^2)L'_N(x) = g(x)$. Let $\{x_n\}$ be the successive approximations through Newton method:

$$x_{n+1} = x_n - \frac{g(x_n)}{g'(x_n)}$$

$$g'(x) = -2xL'_N(x) + (1-x^2)L''_N$$

we know that Legendre polynomial are a solution of the second ordinary differential equation:

$$(1-x^2)y'' - 2xy'(x) + N(N+1)y(x) = 0$$

this lead to:

$$(1-x^2)L''_N - 2xL'_N = -N(N+1)L_N(x)$$

therefore, we get

$$g'(x) = -N(N+1)L_N(x)$$

and then

$$x_{n+1} = x_n - \frac{(1-x^2)L'_N(x)}{-N(N+1)L_N(x)}$$

$$x_{n+1} = x_n + \frac{1}{N(N+1)} \frac{(1-x^2)L'_N(x)}{L_N(x)}$$

then using

$$(x^2 - 1) \frac{L'_N(x)}{N} = xL_N(x) - L_{N-1}(x)$$

$$(1 - x^2) \frac{L'_N(x)}{N} = L_{N-1}(x) - xL_N(x)$$

$$x_{n+1} = x_n + \frac{1}{(N+1)L_N(x)} \cdot \frac{(1-x^2)L'_N(x)}{L_N(x)}$$

$$x_{n+1} = x_n + \frac{1}{(N+1)L_N(x)} \cdot (L_{N-1}(x) - xL_N(x))$$

$$x_{n+1} = x_n + \frac{L_{N-1}(x) - xL_N(x)}{(N+1)L_N(x)}$$

will be used to compute the approximate roots of $(1-x^2)L'_N(x)$ and the Legendre polynomial must be introduced using recursive relation:

$$\begin{cases} (n+1)P_{n+1}(x) = (2n+1)xP_n(x) - nP_{n-1}(x) \\ P_0(x) = 0 \\ P_1(x) = x \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

to compute the zeros of $h_i(x) = (1-x^2)L'_N(x)$. Its enough to compute the zero of $L'_N(x)$ we will use Newton method:

$$x^{k+1} = x^k - \frac{L'_N(x^k)}{L''_N(x^k)}$$

to avoid evaluating the values of L''_N we use

$$L''_N(x) = 2xL'_N(x) - N(N+1)L_N(x)$$

to avoid evaluating the values of L_N'' we use

$$L_N''(x) = 2xL_N'(x) - N(N+1)L_N(x)$$

therefore

$$x^{k+1} = x^k - \frac{L_N'(x^k)}{2xL_N'(x^k) - N(N+1)L_N(x^k)}. \quad (8)$$

For an iterative method, we must chose a good initial guess or initial approximation. The approximation of the zeros of $L_N(x)$ is given by:

$$\sigma = \cos\left(\frac{4k-1}{4N+2}\pi\right) \left(1 - \frac{N-1}{8N^3} - \frac{1}{384N^4} \left(39 - \frac{28}{\sin^2\left(\frac{4k-1}{4N+2}\pi\right)}\right)\right) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{N^5}\right). \quad (9)$$

We know that there is one zero between two consecutive zeros of $L_N(x)$. So we can take as initial guess as the overage of the two roots i.e

$$V^0 = \frac{\sigma_k + \sigma_{k+1}}{2}; \quad 1 \leq k \leq N-1.$$

If we put $\theta_k = \frac{4k-1}{4N+2}\pi$, then

$$\sigma = \cos(\theta_k) \left(1 - \frac{N-1}{8N^3} - \frac{1}{384N^4} \left(39 - \frac{28}{\sin^2(\theta_k)}\right)\right) + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{N^5}\right). \quad (10)$$

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented some analytical and numerical methods for solving the Fredholm integral equation of the second kind. The analytical methods are the degenerate kernel methods, converting Fredholm integral equation to ODE. Moreover, we have used the following numerical methods: Newton method and Legendre polynomial solution of the second ordinary differential equation. The absolute error has approached zero which was shown that numerical results were acceptable.

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